

THE ANTENATAL USE OF BETAMETHASONE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PRETERM INFANTS AT A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Received: May 14, 2025

Accepted: Jun 11, 2025

Published: Jun 27, 2025

ABSTRACT

Objectives: Monitoring the effectiveness of betamethasone on preterm births. Evaluating five components respiratory rate, chest movement, lower chest indentation, nasal flaring, grunting, ensuring health condition of preterm infant using APGAR. **Methods:** In a tertiary care hospital inpatient medical data were the subject of this retrospective observational study carrying out the role of betamethasone in preterm infant's complications. The study uses the application of the APGAR and Silverman-Anderson scores to evaluate the degree of respiratory distress and general health of premature babies. **Results:** The study includes 120 sample size of the subjects of having gestation period from 34 weeks to 36 weeks 6 days, who are under inj. Betamethasone treatment. Out of 120 sample size 20 preterm infants were suffering from moderate RDS and are admitted to NICU for further evaluation. 16.7% of preterm infants are suffering from moderate RDS. 83.3% of preterm infants shown reduced risk of preterm complications. **Conclusion:** The study also covers the application of the APGAR and Silverman-Anderson scores to evaluate the degree of respiratory distress and general health of premature babies. With careful consideration of gestational age and individual patient characteristics, the results of this study justify the routine use of prenatal betamethasone medication in pregnant women at risk of preterm birth.

Keywords: Betamethasone, APGAR score, SAS score, preterm, RDS.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to estimates, 13.4 million of infants were born prior to 37 full weeks of pregnancy in the year of 2020. About 900,000 deaths were caused in 2019 by preterm births problems, making them the top cause of death for children under five. Existing, affordable measures could avert three-quarters of these deaths¹. The percentage of preterm births in 2020 is ranging from 4-16%. Antenatal corticosteroids are very often utilized for pregnant women, at risk of preterm births. Their use grew following a 1994 National Institute of Health consensus conference that found compelling evidence that glucocorticoids, when given to women who are likely to give birth to preterm before 34 weeks of pregnancy period, reduce infant adverse effects, includes death, respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), and other complications².

The capacity of prenatal betamethasone to encourage foetal lung maturation is its main advantage. Underdeveloped lungs are common in preterm newborns, which can result in respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), a disease brought on by insufficient production of surfactant, which is essential for maintaining lung inflation³.

Furthermore, betamethasone indicates in lowering the occurrence of intracranial hemorrhages (brain bleeds) and necrotizing enterocolitis, a potentially fatal intestinal infection. Betamethasone can reduce a premature infant's risk of death by up to 40% while also lowering the risk of respiratory difficulties, cerebral hemorrhages, and necrotizing enterocolitis. It can also decrease the likelihood of a newborn developing problems such as HIE, cerebral palsy, and periventricular leukomalacia⁴. A single dose of betamethasone administered within 3 hours prior to premature birth may decrease the rates of serious outcomes and other morbidities in neonates. Betamethasone's adverse effects are reduced on given small doses late in pregnancy. One dose of corticosteroids is suggested for women of gestation period between 24/07 weeks and 33 6/7 weeks⁵.

The focus of this study is to evaluate respiratory distress, severity and to evaluate response to betamethasone treatment in preterm at tertiary care hospital. Monitoring the effectiveness of betamethasone on preterm births. Evaluating five components respiratory rate, chest movement, lower chest indentation, nasal flaring, grunting, ensuring health condition of preterm infant using APGAR.

2. METHODOLOGY

This is retrospective observational study which is carried out to share the role of betamethasone in management of preterm infants at a tertiary care hospital. This study is conducted in 'MALLA REDDY NARAYANA MULTI-SPECIALITY HOSPITAL'. The study period is organized in the schedule of months i.e. JULY 2024-JAN 2025. The sample size will be 120 individuals collected from obstetrics and gynecology wards, which includes the patients of gestation period from 34 to 36 weeks +6days.

Inclusive criteria: All preterm gestation women (late preterm), Women aged 18 and above, only using betamethasone, Gestation period between 34 to 36weeks +6days.

Exclusive criteria: Less than 34 weeks of gestation period. Smoking and alcohol, Fast onset of labor after administration of betamethasone less than 12 hrs.

Statistical analysis: The Chi-Square test will be used to assess the distribution of APGAR scores and Silverman-Anderson scores among preterm infants whose mothers received antenatal betamethasone.

3. RESULTS

Based on age:

The study includes 120 patients of different ages. 2 patients are of 18 years, 4 patients are of 19 years, 8 patients are of 20 years, 10 patients are of 21, 4 patients are of 22 years, 10 patients are of 23 years, 11 patients are of 25 years, 16 patients are of 26 years, 10 patients are of 27 years, 8 patients are of 28 years, 7 patients are of 29 years, 8 patients are of 30 years, 4 patients are of 31 years, 6 patients are of 32 years, 2 patients are of 33 years, 3 patients are of 34 years.

Fig. 1: Bar graph between age and number of cases

Fig 2: Graph between age and number of cases

Fig 3: Pie chat of preterm mother population based on age

Based on comorbid conditions:

The comorbid conditions that mostly identified from 120 patients are hypothyroid of 13%, hypertension and hypothyroid of 2%, preeclampsia of 6%, gestational diabetes (GDM) of 8%, oligohydramnios of 2%, GDM with hypertension of 1% and with no comorbid conditions is of 68%. Hypothyroid is the most comorbid condition in antenatal mothers.

Fig 4: pie chat of comorbid conditions

Based on severity of RDS:

As per inclusive and exclusive criteria the sample size of 120 has been collected of the patients having gestation period from 34 weeks to 36 weeks 6 days. The measuring parameters are APGAR and SAS score, the APGAR score is mostly found between 7- 9. The SAS score is varying depending on different individuals and their conditions. Out of 120 patients 20 premature babies are affected with moderate RDS condition. 16.67% of patients are affected with moderate RDS. They are admitted to NICU for further evaluation.

34 weeks of gestation period:

Depending on different gestation periods, the data is analysed, and the result has found as following. There are 8 patients are affected with moderate RDS in between 34 weeks to 34 weeks and 6 days out of 120 sample size. The prevalence of moderate RDS within 34 weeks to 34 weeks 6 days is 6.67%. The SAS score of moderate RDS patients is between 4-6 indicating moderate RDS where the respiratory rate of these scores is between 60- 79 beats per minute.

35 weeks of gestation period

The severity of RDS in 35 weeks to 35 weeks 6 days is less compared with 34 weeks of gestation period. There are 4 moderate RDS suffering preterm babies are found in between 35 to 35 weeks 6 days. The prevalence of the moderate RDS in between 35 to 35 weeks and 6 days is 3.3%. Out of 120 preterm 4 preterm infants are affected with moderate RDS in between 35 weeks to 35 weeks and 6 days.

36 weeks of gestation period

The severity of RDS in between 36 weeks to 36 weeks and 6 days are 8 preterm infants affected with moderate RDS. The prevalence of the moderate RDS in between 36 weeks to 36 weeks 6 days of gestation period is 6.67%. Out of 120 preterm babies 8 preterm infants affected with moderate RDS in between 36 weeks to 36 weeks and 6 days. The total prevalence of moderate RDS is 16.67% in the gestation period between 34 weeks to 36 weeks 6 days. The remaining 83.3% of the patients are healthy.

Fig 5: pie chart of preterm NICU admissions based on gestation period

4. DISCUSSION

Our study aimed is to assess the efficacy of antenatal betamethasone utilization in a tertiary care hospital setting, as it has long been a commonly acknowledged practice for the treatment of preterm infants. Since the favorable effects of corticosteroids on the rates of sever outcomes and respiratory distress depend on this interval, the time between the administration of prenatal corticosteroids and preterm birth is crucial. According to the study result, includes 120 preterm infants from 34 weeks to 36weeks 6days, antenatal betamethasone considerably enhanced neonatal outcomes. The significant prevalence of comorbid disorders among the patients was one of our study's main conclusions. The most prevalent comorbid ailment, affecting 13% of the patients, was hypothyroidism. This emphasizes how crucial comprehensive prenatal care and concomitant condition screening are to the best possible management of premature labor. We discovered that across the gestational age strata, APGAR ratings provide significant insight into the likelihood of newborn death among preterm infants. All gestational age strata showed a consistent rise in the relative risk of newborn death in response to a declining APGAR score: however, the increases in relative risk were significantly greater for infants with older gestational ages⁶. Majority of the neonates in our study had APGAR ratings in the range of 7-9. Nevertheless, 20 premature infants (16.6%) experienced moderate respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), necessitating their entry to the newborn intensive care unit (NICU) for additional assessment and care. Our study demonstrates that prenatal corticosteroids can lower the risk of RDS by 80- 85%. To decrease the frequency of RDS and other problems, our study emphasizes the significance of cautious patient selection and monitoring. Our study's SAS scores differed based on the condition of each patient, underscoring the significance of individualized treatment and premature labor management⁷. To guarantee the best results, our study also emphasizes the necessity of careful observation and follow-up with preterm infants. The patients who are found to be suffering from moderate RDS are having the respiratory rate between 60- 79 beats per minute. On further evaluation preterm infants suffering from moderate RDS are admitted to NICU for good improvement of their condition, by ventilation, and further treatment for lung maturation in babies⁸.

5. CONCLUSION

Our findings demonstrate that antenatal betamethasone is linked to lower rates of respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) and better APGAR ratings in preterm infants. Since 32% of patients had one or more comorbid illnesses, with hypothyroidism being the most prevalent, the study emphasises the significance of prenatal care and screening for comorbid conditions. The necessity of individualised treatment and management of preterm labour is highlighted by the high prevalence of comorbid disorders. The results of the study shows prenatal corticosteroids can lower the incidence of RDS by 80-85%. To reduce the likelihood of problems, our study further emphasises the significance of cautious patient selection and monitoring.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to Principal and staff members of Malla Reddy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Maisammaguda, Secunderabad, India, for their technical assistance and the facilities provided for carrying out this work.

REFERENCES

1. Gyamfi-Bannerman C, Thom EA, Blackwell SC, Tita ATN, Reddy UM, Saade GR, et al. Antenatal Betamethasone for Women at Risk for Late Preterm Delivery. *New England Journal of Medicine* [Internet]. 2016 Apr 7;374(14):1311–20.
2. Saldaña-García N, Espinosa-Fernández MG, Martínez-Pajares JD, Tapia-Moreno E, Moreno-Samos M, Cuenca-Marín C, et al. Antenatal Betamethasone Every 12 Hours in Imminent Preterm Labour. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* [Internet]. 2022 Jan 1 [cited 2023 Mar 5]; 11 (5):1227.
4. Gaur K. Effect of Single Dose Betamethasone Administration in Pregnancy on Maternal and Newborn Parameters. *JOURNAL OF CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC RESEARCH*. 2017;
5. Foglia LM, Deering SH, Lim E, Landy H. Maternal glucose levels after dexamethasone for fetal lung development in twin vs singleton pregnancies. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology* [Internet]. 2008 Oct 1 [cited 2024 Sep 11]; 199 (4):380.e1–4.
6. Lungameni J, Nghitanwa EM, Uusiku L, Karera A. Maternal factors associated with immediate low Apgar score in newborn babies at an intermediate hospital in Northern Namibia. *Journal of Public Health in Africa*. 2022 Oct 25; 13 (3).
7. Cnattingius S, Johansson S, Razaz N. Apgar Score and Risk of Neonatal Death among Preterm Infants. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2020 Jul 2; 383(1):49–57.
8. Razaz N, Cnattingius S, Joseph K. Association between Apgar scores of 7 to 9 and neonatal mortality and morbidity: population based cohort study of term infants in Sweden. *BMJ* [Internet]. 2019 May 7; 365:11656.
9. Behrman RE, Adrienne Stith Butler, Institute of Medicine (US) Committee on Understanding Premature Birth and Assuring Healthy Outcomes. *Mortality and Acute Complications in Preterm Infants* [Internet]. Nih.gov. National Academies Press (US); 2010.